

AWARENESS REGARDING POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME AMONG FEMALES OF THE REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Abstract

Background: Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is a common hormonal disorder among women of reproductive age, marked by irregular menstruation, elevated androgens, and ovarian cysts. It is influenced by genetic, hormonal, and lifestyle factors. Despite its prevalence, many cases remain undiagnosed due to limited awareness and inadequate screening.

Objective: To assess the level of awareness regarding PCOS among women of reproductive age and evaluate their related health practices.

Materials and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 350 women aged 18–30 at Punjab College Campus A, Lahore, using convenient sampling. Data were collected through a semi-structured questionnaire covering demographics, PCOS knowledge, and lifestyle practices. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 24.

Results: While 71.4% had heard of PCOS and 82.3% showed good awareness, only 42% exhibited healthy lifestyle practices, reflecting a significant knowledge–practice gap.

Conclusion: Awareness does not translate into healthy behaviors. Targeted health education and lifestyle intervention programs are needed to improve prevention and management outcomes.

1. Introduction

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a widespread and complex hormonal disorder affecting women of reproductive age, with global prevalence ranging from 5% to 21%, and higher rates reported in South Asian populations (Ye et al., 2021; Han et al., 2023). The condition is characterized by irregular menstrual cycles, hyperandrogenism, and ovarian cysts. Its etiology involves genetic and epigenetic influences, hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis dysfunction, insulin resistance, and metabolic factors. High-fat dietary patterns and obesity further aggravate hormonal imbalance, inflammation, and metabolic disturbances, worsening reproductive

symptoms (Zhang et al., 2024). Effective management requires combined strategies, including lifestyle modification, emotional support, and medical intervention.

PCOS often emerges during adolescence; however, diagnosing the condition in this age group is challenging due to overlapping symptoms of normal puberty. Emerging diagnostic approaches, such as anti-Mullerian hormone assessment and improved ultrasound criteria, are being explored to enhance early detection (Yachmaneni Jr. et al., 2023). Beyond reproductive concerns, PCOS is associated with pregnancy complications, including gestational diabetes and preeclampsia (Adu-Bonsaffoh et al., 2022). The

psychological burden, including anxiety, depression, and body-image distress, is frequently overlooked despite its significant impact on quality of life (Cheshire et al., 2024).

Although PCOS is common, awareness remains limited, leading to delayed diagnosis and poor symptom management. Misconceptions and lack of knowledge about long-term health risks, such as insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes, persist among many women (Jabeen et al., 2022). Raising awareness is essential, as informed women are more likely to seek timely care and adopt healthier behaviors (Ee et al., 2021; Cheshire et al., 2024). Therefore, this study aims to evaluate awareness and knowledge regarding PCOS among female students in Punjab College Lahore to identify gaps and help guide targeted educational interventions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Design and Setting:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess awareness and health-related practices regarding PCOS among young females. The study was carried out at Saida Waheed FMH College of Nursing in collaboration with Punjab College Lahore (Campus 3A) over a period of six months, from October 2024 to March 2025.

2.2 Study Population and Sample Size:

The target population included females aged 18–30 years. A sample size of 350 participants was calculated using Dobson’s formula $n = z^2 P (1-P) / d^2$, based on a prevalence of 28%, 95% confidence interval, and 5% margin of error. A total of 350 questionnaires were distributed to enhance result validity.

2.3 Sampling Technique and Selection Criteria:

Convenience sampling was used.

3. Results

TABLE 1: Demographic characteristics of participants of students of college. (N=350).

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-25	264	75.4
26-30	68	19.4
31-35	10	2.9
36-40	8	2.3

Inclusion criteria: females aged 18–30 years with established menarche.

Exclusion criteria: females from medical backgrounds or those with gynecological disabilities or comorbidities.

2.4 Data Collection Procedure:

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Fatima Memorial Hospital. Permission was granted by the college administration prior to data collection. Participants were informed about the study purpose, and written consent was obtained. A structured session was conducted, questionnaires were distributed and collected, and a brief educational talk on PCOS was delivered afterward.

2.5 Data Collection Tool:

A structured, pilot-tested questionnaire was used, consisting of:

1. **Demographics** (age, marital status, education),
2. **PCOS Awareness** (20 knowledge-based items scored as correct/incorrect),
3. **Health-Related Practices** (10 lifestyle behavior items rated on a 5-point Likert scale).

2.6 Ethical Considerations:

The study followed the Declaration of Helsinki guidelines. Participation was voluntary, confidentiality was maintained, and no harm was caused.

2.7 Data Analysis:

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 24. Descriptive statistics were applied to summarize sample characteristics and key study outcomes.

Marital Status		
Single	315	90.0
Married	35	10.0
Education level		
Intermediate or above	350	100
Area of Study involve		
Arts	53	15.4
Sciences	297	84.6
Employment status		
Students	350	100

Study showed that majority (82.3%) of young girls at their reproductive age had good awareness regarding PCOS. And 17% had poor knowledge. Majority had good practices regarding disease due to their good knowledge.

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of participants in which majority of respondents 264

(75.4%) are between the age of 20-25 years. Among them 315 (90%) females were single, while only 35(10%) were married. All participants were students 350 (100%) with intermediate or above education level. Majority of the participants 297(84.6%) were from health-related fields.

Table 2: Awareness of PCOS among Reproductive age women of Punjab college campus 3A (N=350).

Sr no.	Items	Frequency	Percentage
1	Have you heard about the term called “polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)”?		
	No	100	28.6
	Yes	250	71.4
2	Have you heard about the androgen (male) hormone? E.g. testosterone		
	No	123	35.1
	Yes	227	64.9
3	In PCOS, there is an increased level of androgen level.		
	No	79	22.6
	Yes	271	77.4
4	Patients suffering from PCOS have small multiple cysts in their ovaries.		
	No	117	33.4
	Yes	233	66.6
5	Obesity may cause PCOS.		
	No	70	20.0
	Yes	280	80.0
6	Prediabetes condition (due to decreased insulin action in the body) may cause PCOS.		
	No	86	24.6
	Yes	264	75.4
7	Irregular or absence of menstrual (periods) cycle is a symptom of PCOS.		
	No	58	16.6

	Yes	292	83.4
8	An unusual amount of hair growth on different body parts (upper lip, chin, abdomen, breast, thighs etc.) is a symptom of PCOS.		
	No	54	15.4
	Yes	296	84.6
9	Severe acne problem during the menstrual (periods) cycle is a symptom of PCOS.		
	No	40	11.4
	Yes	310	88.6
10	Hair loss from the scalp more than normal is a symptom of PCOS.		
	No	69	19.7
	Yes	281	80.3
11	PCOS diagnosis can be confirmed by vaginal ultrasound.		
	No	80	22.9
	Yes	270	77.1
12	A specific blood test can be used for the diagnosis of PCOS		
	No	46	13.1
	Yes	304	86.9
13	PCOS may lead to diabetes (long-term high blood sugar level).		
	No	76	21.7
	Yes	274	78.3
14	PCOS may lead to heart diseases.		
	No	78	22.3
	Yes	272	77.7
15	PCOS may lead to infertility (inability to have children) or reduced fertility (reduced chance to get pregnant).		
	No	48	13.7
	Yes	302	86.3
16	PCOS may lead to anxiety and depression.		
	No	43	12.3
	Yes	307	87.7
17	Hormonal therapy (oral contraceptives, hormone, intrauterine device etc) may be used to treat PCOS.		
	No	30	8.6
	Yes	320	91.4
18	Anti-diabetic medications (metformin) may be used to treat PCOS.		
	No	63	18.0

	Yes	287	82.0
19	Symptomatic treatment (clomiphene, letrozole, acne topical cream, spironolactone etc.) may be given to relieve the symptoms of PCOS.		
	No	40	11.4
	Yes	310	88.6
20	Surgery may be used to remove ovarian cysts		
	No	65	18.6
	Yes	285	81.4

Table 2 shows the Awareness of PCOS among Reproductive age women's in which A significant proportion of females 250 (71.4%) have heard about PCOS. Similarly 227 (64.9%) females agree that they have heard about the androgen (male) hormone. Majority of participants 271 (77.4%) correctly identify that PCOS involves increased androgen (male hormone) levels. However 233(66.6%) participants understand that multiple ovarian cysts are a characteristic of PCOS. 280(80.0%) females recognize the link between obesity and PCOS. While 264 (75.4%) are aware that prediabetes condition can cause PCOS. A bulk of females 292(83.4%) agree that Irregular or absence of menstrual cycle is a symptom of PCOS. Similarly 296 (84.6%) females agree that an unusual amount of hair growth on different body parts is a symptom of PCOS. Majority of the female 310(88.6%) agree that Severe acne problem during the menstrual cycle is a symptom of PCOS.

About 281(80.3%) females agree that Hair loss from the scalp more than normal is a symptom of PCOS. While 270 (77.1%) females agree that PCOS diagnosis can be confirmed by vaginal ultrasound. Similarly 304 (86.9%) participants agree that blood test can be used for the diagnosis of PCOS. About 274(78.3%) females agree that PCOS may lead to diabetes and 272(77.7%) females agree that PCOS lead to heart diseases. Majority of the females 302 (86.3%) agree that PCOS lead to infertility. A bulk of females 307(87.7%) agree that PCOS lead to anxiety and depression. However 320(91.4%) participants agree that Hormonal therapy used to treat PCOS. Similarly 287(82.0%) females agree that Anti-diabetic medications used to treat PCOS. About 310 (88.6%) females agree that Symptomatic treatment given to relieve the symptoms of PCOS. Similarly 285(81.4%) females agree that treatment through Surgery used to remove ovarian cysts.

Table 3: Mean score of Awareness of PCOS among Reproductive age women's (N=350)

	N	Mean ±SD	Minimum	Maximum
Awareness score	350	36.1 ±1.97	20	40
Awareness percentage score	350	90.2±4.93	57	100

Table 3 consists of 20 items questionnaire was used to determine the Awareness of PCOS among Reproductive age women's. An awareness

percentage score about PCOS among women at reproductive age was 90.2±4.93with score range of 20-40.

Table 4: Awareness level about PCOS (N=350)

Awareness level	Percentage
Good awareness	>85%
Poor awareness	<85%

The overall awareness level was categories using bloom cutoff value > 85 shows good awareness level and < 50 show poor awareness level.

Table 5: Health-Related Practice

Items	FREQUENY	PERCENTAGE
How often do you read nutrition labels?		
Never	48	13.7
Rarely	79	22.6
Sometimes	125	35.7
Usually	59	16.9
Always	39	11.1
I incorporate low-fat foods into my diet.		
Never	40	11.4
Rarely	67	19.1
Sometimes	133	38.0
Usually	70	20.0
Always	40	11.4
I incorporate low salt foods into my diet.		
Never	45	12.9
Rarely	71	20.3
Sometimes	128	36.6
Usually	66	18.9
Always	40	11.4
I eat 5 servings of fruits and vegetables per day.		
Never	30	8.6
Rarely	82	23.4
Sometimes	142	40.6
Usually	61	17.4
Always	35	10.0
I decrease the amount of refined sugar in my diet		
Never	29	8.3
Rarely	65	18.6
Sometimes	135	38.6
Usually	74	21.1
Always	47	13.4
I eat more high-fiber foods.		
Never	45	12.9
Rarely	74	21.1
Sometimes	132	37.7
Usually	60	17.1
Always	39	11.1
I eat smaller portions at dinner.		
Never	50	14.3
Rarely	76	21.7
Sometimes	122	34.9

Usually	60	17.1
Always	41	11.7
I exercise 30 minutes 5 days a week.		
Never	50	14.3
Rarely	79	22.6
Sometimes	122	34.9
Usually	59	16.9
Always	40	11.4
I control my eating on weekends.		
Never	35	10.0
Rarely	85	24.3
Sometimes	125	35.7
Usually	65	18.6
Always	40	11.4
It is easy for me to eat a healthy diet.		
Never	44	12.6
Rarely	67	19.1
Sometimes	127	36.3
Usually	67	19.1
Always	45	12.9

Table 5 shows the health-related practice of females in which 125 (35.7%) females sometimes read nutrition labels. Similarly 133(38.0%) females sometimes incorporate low-fat foods into diet. About 128(36.6%) females sometimes incorporate low salt foods into diet. However 142(40.6%) females sometimes eat 5 servings of fruits and vegetables per day. A bulk of females 135(38.6%) sometimes decrease the amount of

refined sugar from diet. Similarly 132 (37.7%) females sometimes eat high-fiber foods. About 122 (34.9%) females sometimes eat smaller portions at dinner. Similarly 122(34.9%) females sometimes exercise 30 minutes 5 days in a week. however 125(35.7%) sometimes control their eating on weekends. Majority of females 127(36.3%) sometimes find easy to eat a healthy diet.

Table 6: Mean score Health Related Practice of PCOS among Reproductive age women’s (N=350)

	N	Mean ±SD	Minimum	Maximum
Practice score	350	29.6±3.69	10	50
Practice percentage score	350	59.3±7.38	36	80

Table 6 consists of 10 items questionnaire was used to determine the Health Related Practice of PCOS among Reproductive age women’s. Practice

percentage score about PCOS among women at reproductive age was 59.3±7.38 with score range of 10-50.

Table 7: Practice level about PCOS (N=350)

Practice level	Percentage
Good practice	>60%
Average practice	50-60
Poor practice	<50%

The overall practice level was categories using bloom cutoff value >60 shows good practice level, 50-60% shows average practice and < 50 show poor practice level.

4. Discussion

To manage PCOS the first step is awareness and accurate diagnosis, both of which can upgrade quality of life (QOL) in patient. Study was conducted which showed that majority of young girls at their reproductive age had good awareness regarding PCOS while few had poor knowledge. Moreover study confirmed that majority had good practices too.

According to the study Out of 350 participants, 292(83.4%) participants had menstrual irregularities and these irregularities have a participative role in PCOS. Similar to this study Zaitoun, B. et al in 2020 reported that 62.60% participants had menstrual irregularities. Obesity is contributing factor for development of metabolic diseases like PCOS. Study revealed that majority (80%) young girls were known that obesity is major contributor; similar result was reported in a study that was done by Begum, G. et al (2024). Their study showed that 50% of girls with PCOS are having central obesity. And this condition often arises from excessive consumption of fast food and irregular eating habits.

Some studies had contrary results regarding this, Such as increase the risk of heart disease. A study revealed that maximum Participants had knowledge that PCOS lead to heart disease. A study done by Zaitoun, B. et al. reported that majority were not aware that PCOS increases risk for heart diseases.

Infertility is very common in girls that are suffering from PCOS. This syndrome leads to infertility .The study discloses that 86.3% participants were known. With Contrast to this study another study done by Patel ,J., & Rai , S.(2018) confess that only 50.68% women had awareness regarding connection with this syndrome.

Skin problems like acne, acne scars and hirsutism etc. are causative factors of PCOS. The study reflected that 88.6% girls were aware about acne issues in PCOS. And 84.6% girls had awareness about causative factor of hirsutism. In opposition to this study Safdar, N. A. et al.(2023) reported that 39.33% were well aware regarding acne issues,

and 22% reported hirsutism effect on chin 40% reported on chest and thighs.

5. Conclusion

PCOS is a significant yet unrecognized health problem that effect both reproductive and metabolic health. With increasing awareness through education interventions can help women identify symptoms early, seek medical assistance and adopt healthy lifestyles. This study underscores the importance of improving PCOS education among young women to evaluate this long term health outcome.

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